

INFRASTRUCTURAL PROVISION AND QUALITY OF LIFE AMONG RURAL DWELLERS IN NORTHERN SENATORIAL DISTRICT, CROSS RIVER STATE. NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT:

The paper examined the level at which infrastructural provision affects wellbeing, progress and quality of life of citizens, due to the declining level of infrastructures in country, highlighting the challenges and opportunities in improving the well-being of the citizens. The major objective of this study was to investigate how poor or non-availability of basic infrastructures affect human physical and mental wellbeing of Rural Dwellers of Cross River Northern Senatorial District. Despite steady economic growth, Nigeria faces significant development hurdles, including poverty, inequality and limited access to health care and education. The study employed the mixed-method approach as its research design, sample of 280 were selected through The Multi Stage sampling technique, purposive and proportionate techniques. Both qualitative and quantitative were employed for data collection, data were analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation. The study reviews relevant literature on the topic, and adopted, The Endogenous and, Human Development Theory/Capabilities Approach as its Theoretical Framework. The study concluded through its findings that, there is acute deficit and decay in the existing infrastructures in study area and the entire country in general. Recommendations include, government should invest in human capital development, promote provision and maintenance of basic infrastructures across the country, address social inequality and improve governance.

Keywords: Infrastructure, Provision, Quality of Life, Human Capital, Development.

INTRODUCTION:

Infrastructure provision is very crucial to development and growth of a country. It improves standard of living and health challenges. The provision of adequate infrastructure and basic amenities in rural areas in Nigeria is very important. The development of rural areas worldwide has a challenge to professionals in developed cities, when considering development, socio-cultural and political activities. Oyedele (2012).

Infrastructure provide strength to economic development by increasing productivity through the provision of basic services, this increases the provision of conducive environment for both commercial activities and human living standard. The Cross River Northern Senatorial District, is one of the important parts of cross river state and south-south region of Nigeria. because the entire zone and neighbouring state depends on themselves in terms of cross-border

trade both legal and illegal. Therefore, these activities depend on road and others infrastructure to provide enabling environment and better living standard. Aluko (2012).

Nigeria, Africa's largest economy, has experienced steady economic growth, yet its human development indicators remain low. The country's quality of life is affected by various factors, including poverty, inequality, and limited access to healthcare and education. This paper aims to explore the relationship between infrastructures and quality of life. The usual measurement or estimation of standard of living in terms of GNI or GDP per capital is inadequate to appropriately estimate or improvement in living standards, since it does not factor in aspects of well-being that are not determined by the purchasing power of private incomes (Craft 1997:229).

Infrastructure provision in rural areas needs urgent attention due to its importance in a particular environment. The appropriate laws and conduction guiding provision of infrastructure is favourable to the area, misappropriation of fund and zoning strategy of policy makers do not rural areas. In Nigeria, socio-political institutions and structures are arranged in such a way that national income is concentrated in the hands of the privileged few. Thus, the proportion of the Nigeria's population truly living in abject poverty increases yearly. Little wonder Nigeria became the poverty capital of the world in 2018 with 86.9 million people living below the international poverty level of \$1.90 per day (Brookings Institution, as quoted in Okagba, 2019: Para 1).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Lack of infrastructure and basic services has been identified as major contributors to poor quality of life among rural communities in Nigeria. So far, Nigeria's economic growth has not translated to improved quality of life for its citizens, with many Nigerians living in poverty and having limited access to healthcare, security and education. When there are deficiencies in these necessities of life that enhance well-being, such as lack of access to good health care, good food, sources of portable water, good and affordable housing, healthy environment, and quality of education, and if the actual proportion of the population who cannot afford these basic essentials for a minimum standard of living, outnumbers the few privileged ones, then there are bound to be crisis. (UNDP, 2019).

Currently, the country is faced with the challenges of high transportation, higher cost of living, communal crisis, poor quality education, non-availability of basic healthcare services, kidnapping, herdsmen, etc. These are direct consequences of systemic failure. Statistics have shown a constant rising trend in government capital and recurrent expenditure for the past 3 decades which unfortunately has not been able to translate into meaningful development and growth as Nigeria is still listed among the poorest countries of the world. (Olugbenga & Owoye, 2017). Many people in Nigeria are still living below the poverty line (Cooray, 2019).

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The major objective of this study is to investigate how poor or non-availability of basic infrastructures affect the physical and mental wellbeing of Rural Dwellers of Cross River Northern Senatorial District. Also;

To examine the current state of Nigeria's Infrastructure and its impact on quality of life of the rural populace.

To identify the challenges faced and the opportunities available in improving the quality of life in Nigeria.

To propose recommendations for governments, policymakers and politicians to addressing these challenges.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Provision of Infrastructure in Nigeria

The socio-economic development of any nation hinges on social and economic infrastructures available in the nation. Infrastructures are the structures upon which the operation of a society depends. Infrastructure provision helps provide employment and improve quality of life. Infrastructure like roads, markets, security and telecommunication directly impact commerce. Effective infrastructure development involves Needs Assessment, Project Management, Value for money Analysis and efficient Monitoring and Evaluation. DSM (2012)., Kimba. (2012). The challenges relating to infrastructure provision are numerous developing countries including Nigeria, scholars in various field pointed out the causes which include finance, modern technology for infrastructure development, maintenance and design of the projects, quality requirements of projects to meet international standard and to be sustainably developed. Lack of data on population and spending, environmental effects. Dearth of visionary leader, Demand and supply, Procurement method and corruption, non-adherence basic principles of project management. Olotutuah and Taiwo (2015).

In Nigeria as other Africa countries, sustainable infrastructure is not only needed to increase socioeconomic growth, but also to strengthen inhabitant's empowerment aids poverty reduction in order to elevate standard of living. Obokoh and Goldman (2016). Development of rural communities with infrastructural facilities is a major step towards stemming the tides in communal crisis and long-term effect will be effective management of subsequent crisis in the rural areas.

Kimba. (2012). found that, infrastructure development like roads, electricity, and water provisions, reduces the services and hygiene within the territory if there are inadequate, or absent in the area. Development take place in line with industrialization, population increase, and changing settlement patterns therefore, governments need to provide basic infrastructures for the desired change. Edun, Akinde and Idowu (2013).

Quality of Life in Nigeria

Quality of life is also related to the sustainability in a community, the development of sustainability dwells on meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. (Ekpo, Okon & Beredugo, 2019). However, quality of life is highly relative and differs among clans and jurisdictions. In relation to the Nigeria societal particularly, the following represents attributes of quality of life in the Nigerian context to include: qualities of education, healthcare, employment and income equality.

The quality of life for an individual can vary drastically depending on location, income, and access to resources. Despite being a middle-income country, over 50% of the population

lives in poverty. While official unemployment rate has recently dropped, youth unemployment remains a major challenge, driving many into the informal sector. High inflation and rising cost for essential goods like food and oil exacerbate financial hardship for low and average-wage earners. Akinyemi, Owoaje, Popoola & Ilesanmi (2012).

Access to basic amenities and services; water and sanitation, only three out of five households have access to clean, portable and drinkable water, with even lower access rates in rural areas. Many communities lack basic sanitation facilities. Power supply is unreliable and inconsistent, with frequent outage, only about half of all households have access to electricity, and a constant supply is not guaranteed even with high and outrageous bills. Onwuka. (2021).

Access to quality healthcare services remains limited, especially in rural and most urban centres, citizens faces major infrastructure challenges due to insufficient funding and lack of maintenance culture. Insecurity is a critical concern with common issues like Armed robbery, kidnapping, insurgency, extortion, armed conflicts. Adebayo. (2018).

In Aigbokhan's (2018) opinion, the decline in poverty (if any) resulted by economic growth would be of much greater magnitude if reduction in inequality takes place or is achieved simultaneously. Galor (2020) is of the opinion that their income inequality may subsequently rise after getting declined under certain conditions. This may occur above same threshold of income Galor and Isiddon (2016) are of the opinion that inequality is the essential of growth at early stages but it eventually subsides when the prosperity sets in and benefits start pouring in. Galor (2020) examine that their inequality maybe directly proportional to economic growth when development is achieved through accumulation of physical capital, whereas the change in approach of development alters the scenario by 180 degrees. It implies that inequality is reduced when the prime engine of growth is human capital accumulation rather than the former.

Social inequality result from a society organized by hierarchies of class, race and gender equally distributes access to resources and rights (Ashley, 2020). It can manifest in a variety of ways, like income and wealth inequality, unequal access to education and cultural resources, and differential treatment by the police and judicial system among others.

Education is the cornerstone of societal development, with quality and accessible education serving as fundamental indicators of social wealth and quality of life. The quality of education and the ease of access to it reflects a society's commitment to equipping its citizen with skills, knowledge, and opportunities for advancement. World Bank (2024). In Nigeria, education quality and access have shown gradual improvement; however, regional disparities, economic barriers, and challenges in infrastructures continue to hinder equitable education for all. Although primary to secondary school education in public schools in most states in Nigeria is nominally free, many children still do not attend school due to poverty, lack of facilities, and social factors. Okafor & Eze (2020).

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on two major theories; Endogenous Growth Theory and Human development Theory/Capabilities Approach respective.

Endogenous Growth Theory

The Endogenous Growth Theory was first developed by Paul Romer in 1986, though there are other proponents like, Robert Lucas, Sergio Rebello, Gene Grossman and Elhanan

Helpmann. The theory offers valuable framework for understanding the major drivers of economic development and the importance of investing in human capital development, education and innovation. This theory emphasizes that long term economic growth is driven by endogenous factors such as human capital, technological innovation, and institutional quality, rather than solely external factor, it explains how investment in education, skills development and resources can leads to sustained economic growth. It also highlights the critical role of strong institutions and policies in fostering growth and better life for masses. As valuable as theory might be, its not without limitations, Complexity, Data requirements, Assumptions, External factors, Income inequality are some of the areas of low score.

Human development Theory/Capabilities Approach

This theory, by Amartya Sen and Martha Nussbaum in 1985 and 1990, emphasizes the importance of expanding people's capabilities and freedoms to improve their quality of life. In the context of rural infrastructure, this theory suggests that access to basic infrastructure such as healthcare, education, and sanitation can enhance people's capabilities and improve their quality of life. the Human Development Index (HDI), moves beyond mere economic growth (like GDP) to evaluate actual improvements in people's lives. This framework is crucial for explaining why Nigeria's economic growth often doesn't translate into improved quality of life for its citizens. It provides the tools to analyze how factors like access to clean water, healthcare, and education directly impact human well-being, regardless of the overall GDP growth rate.

Methodology

This study adopted a cross-sectional research design. The population was made up of residence living in the old Ogoja, Headquarter of Cross River State Northern Senatorial District, Nigeria. Two hundred and eighty (280) consenting male and female adults were sampled as respondents using multi stage sampling technique. The area was divided into 10 enumeration areas using the cluster sampling. A total of four (4) numeration areas were randomly were randomly selected from the 10 clusters. Each of the enumeration areas had 15-30 households and about 350-450 people. The purposive sampling was used to select participants at their various households. The research instrument used in the study was a standardized self-report questionnaire divided into four sections. The questionnaire elicited biographical information, which included years of experience and occupations of respondents. The WHO quality of life (WHOQOL-BREF) questionnaire was used to measure physical health, psychological (mental) health and social relationships of respondents. The WHOQOL- BREF has a meritorious reliability (a =0.86) (Gureje, Kola, Afolabi and Olley, 2012). combining qualitative and quantitative data to examine the relationship between Infrastructure provision and quality of life rural dwellers. The study drew on existing literature, statistical data, and case studies.

Conclusion

Provision and maintenance of basic infrastructure in Nigeria cities is one of the best solutions to improving the quality of life of Nigerians. The challenges of sustainable development of infrastructure in Nigerian cities are many. The demand for infrastructure outweighs the supply and capital that can finance rapid provision is lame.

Due to wide gap between infrastructure provision and needs, the leadership classes are in arrears in all sectors. The political culture and style of politicking can not attract foreign investors. Governments do not set the priority right in infrastructure development. Certain infrastructure is supposed to meet specific needs, but most times, government and even public private-partners embarked upon white elephant projects.

Good governance and accountability will be the only antidote to resolving the infrastructure issues, it reduces corruption and minimizes resource wastage through inefficiency. And ensure equitable distribution of infrastructural and developmental projects base on fairness and need. This will improve the quality of life for all Nigeria.

Recommendations

The study among other things recommends the following;

Huge Government and Private partnership Investments in Human Capital development strides; through Increased funding for the educational sector, healthcare services, provision of basic amenities to improve quality of life and promote human dignity and healthy living.

Address social Inequality: Implement policies to address regional disparities and inequality, promote transparency, reduce corruption, such as social protection programs and infrastructure development especially in rural areas.

Promote and encourage the provision of infrastructure: Through strengthening of government institutions, Partners and Dono-Agencies for enhanced performance and productivity, in the provision and maintenance of basic infrastructure, and to ensure effective implementations of policies and programs.

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